

DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE THROUGH IMPROVING SPIRITUAL EDUCATION IN STUDENTS AND YOUNG PEOPLE

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Abstract. *In this article, the unique spiritual features of the current era, the integration of education in the process of continuous education, including cooperation with the family and neighborhood, the realization of consistency between them, and the establishment of effective cooperation of pedagogical teams of educational institutions are described as a social necessity. Recommendations are given to improve the effectiveness of formation of understanding, knowledge, skills and qualifications in students and youth.*

Keywords: *spiritual education, healthy generation, students-youth, continuous education, cooperation, education-education, professional competence, social, value, work, pedagogical demand, pedagogical influence, development.*

The reform, it is expedient to create a general secondary education program in the form of preschool, primary, general education and extracurricular education.

Preschool education aims to shape the child's personality in a healthy and mature way, ready for school. This education is carried out in the family from six to seven years of age, in kindergarten and in other educational institutions, regardless of the form of ownership, in partnership with the school and the community.

In preparing children for school, it is necessary to provide organizational, psychological and methodological support for family upbringing. Pre-school education, family and community cooperation play a solid role in creating a creative person who will raise our country to the level of the great Kindergarten-school cooperation is based, firstly, on the continuity of kindergarten and school, the educational work directed at the requirements of the school for children to achieve the necessary level of general development, and secondly, the teacher's level of development of older preschoolers, children's knowledge, skills and abilities. can be seen as a meaningful, two-way communication that implies active access to the educational process.

The effectiveness of teaching children in school will largely depend on their level of preparation t state of the future.

Readiness for school is an important outcome of the education and upbringing given to a child of preschool age by the partnership of the kindergarten family and the community. Going to school is a normal lifestyle in every child's life. A distinctive feature of our time is the constant improvement of the content of school education. Modern school does not require any special knowledge and skills from a student entering the 1st grade, but more complex forms of mental activity than in previous years, a higher level of moral and volitional qualities, the ability to control their behavior, great business acumen.

The task of the kindergarten is to prepare children for school with the whole system of educational work in a school that fully meets the requirements of modern school education.

An important condition for the practical implementation of consistency in kindergarten and school age is the establishment of work cooperation between educators of preparatory groups and first grade teachers.

The peculiarities of the present period are the family rapprochement of the kindergarten with the school, family and community, which creates an existing social basis for the implementation of consistency between kindergarten, school and the effective cooperation of kindergartens and schools, pedagogical communities of parents.

The main task of cooperation between teachers, kindergarten teachers, family, community is to ensure a high level of unity in preparing children for school, which then leads to successful schooling.

The family is the most important place of education, where mother and father were and remain the natural guardians of their children. The desired task of the educator should be solved in one direction, with the general aspirations of the school and the family.

A.S.Makarenko, as a supporter of the leading role of social education in shaping the personality, emphasized the primacy of social and family goals, the dependence of family education on the "order of society". "Every father and every mother should know what they want to bring up in their child," he wrote.

He urged the teaching staff to study their family life in order to improve the life and upbringing of children and influence parents.

In the current situation, there are serious requirements for the level of preparation of children for school and the need to develop the necessary measures in connection with this. In accordance with the Regulations on preschool education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, preschool education is carried out at home: through the independent education of parents or in stationary preschool institutions, as well as in special groups created in kindergartens, schools, neighborhoods or for children who are not involved in preschool educational centers.

Pre-school education is a key condition in determining the level of readiness of a child of 6-7 years old for school or the need to ensure a smooth transition from the educational environment of kindergarten to the educational environment of a general education school.

The transition of a preschooler to school always leads to significant changes in his life, behavior, interests, everyday relationships. Therefore, it is necessary to acquaint the preschooler with knowledge, ideas, skills and abilities that are not difficult in the process of preparing for schooling in kindergarten or at home. Such acquaintance, in turn, helps the child to go through the period of adaptation without serious difficulties. According to leading experts, "while the concept school readiness includes physical, personal-psychological, mental and special areas of preparing a child for school, this issue needs to be studied by scientists and teachers as an urgent problem of pedagogy.

It is well known that correct and conscious education ensures the humanity of a person. This requires a person of professional maturity, moral maturity and intellectual potential, as well as spiritual height.

Therefore, it is necessary to ensure that young people do not get lost on the path of life, protect them from the storms of time, repeatedly explain to people (educators, teachers), the general public that education is a matter of life and death. In this case, the spiritual and

immunological education of students (MIT) is extremely important, thanks to which ideological gaps can be avoided. At the same time, all of the above indicates the importance, diversity and relevance of the activities that need to be carried out in the field of education.

These requirements should be taken into account in all educational institutions of the country, because education should begin in the womb. We found it necessary to express their sequence as follows:

1. Preschool education. At the same time, parents need to know when to start raising a child, to consciously master the conditions for the birth of a healthy child, to perfection to have a parental example in the upbringing of children, and especially to know and understand the care of children. our government. Parents also have access to our rich national and spiritual heritage, handouts based on the teachings of our ancestors and motherly love, colorful picture books and books that positively influence the upbringing of their children. it is desirable that cartoons convey their vision to their children and pay special attention to attention to important aspects of raising your child. Through them, parents can form elements of high human qualities in their children. At this time, the upbringing of our children at home, in the “Apartment Kindergarten”, in the “Farm Kindergarten” and in the “Kindergarten-Preschool Education” will begin. It is advisable to educate children on pedagogical requirements. Because discipline is formed on the basis of pedagogical requirements in relations between young people begin to form a culture of communication, mutual friendship begins to be understood, respect for parents and their mentors begins to form. In this regard, it is important to inform young people about good and bad habits and their positive and negative consequences for achieving emergence.

2. Education in the system of general secondary education. At the same time, it is necessary to work in assor dance with general secondary education in order to achieve the following promising results: striving for good; be able to think independently; be able to analyze; To be able to feel the feeling of the motherland, to awaken love for the native language; Live grief in the homeland; strengthening respect for our national values; Understanding what nostalgia is; veneration a woman who is a symbol of goodness; arouse pride in the contribution of our great compatriots to the development of the worldview and Islamic culture in mystical ethics; awaken a conscious attitude towards our traditions; create in the minds of young people a perfect image of a prosperous and free Motherland, free and prosperous life, based on the historical and philosophical roots of our national ideology; peace and prosperity of the country, the development of the Motherland and the education of a harmoniously developed generation.

3. Education in the system of higher education. First of all, the socio-economic and cultural development of the republic will be taken into account, the historical and philosophical roots of our national ideology, as well as the rich scientific heritage of our hadith scholars and will be taken into account. In the education of students, attention should be paid to: the training of professionally mature specialists with high human qualities, sprinkled with noble ideas; the foundations of social cooperation, interethnic harmony, interreligious tolerance to educate a spiritually mature person with irrigated; to educate a specialist with a high national mentality and strong ideological immunity, not susceptible to the influence of alien and harmful destructive ideas, to educate students in the spirit of spiritual renewal, self-awareness and active participation in reforms in this area.

4. Postgraduate education. At the same time, education is based on the dialogue of teachers (monologues, dialogues, disputes, conversations, documentaries, etc.), and special attention is paid

to the formation of faith in complete independence in the minds of people. Attention will also be paid to the historical roots and traditions of our national and moral values, the significance of our sacred religion in the spiritual uplift of society.

At the same time, in this part of education, there is a conscious awareness by a person of his rights around him or to protect himself from possible negative influences, to pursue his interests in harmony with the interests of the people and the country. Of particular importance in this regard are meetings, conversations, open dialogues and exhibitions on topics such as "Religion and Culture", "State Policy in the Field of Religion", "Consequences of Fanaticism and Its Negative Consequences", "Causes of Terrorism".

The tasks arising from the stated requirement and the sequence of training in the system of continuous education, first of all, must be correctly understood, otherwise the task may be set and not completed. In this regard, it is advisable that any conscientious member of our society take on the following responsibility:

- active participation in the upbringing and formation of a harmoniously developed generation, strengthening the independence of our independent state;
- education of the younger generation as a harmonious, spiritually mature personality;
- To bring up an ideal person capable of making a worthy contribution to the development of our country.

The current generation lives in a new century - "XXI century - an intellectual century" and in the era of civilization. In this civilization, education, work, creativity is hard work, constant learning, only a person who is able to constantly develop his spiritual culture and spend the results of his education on the development of his family, his people and his state can be an active participant in this civilization.

Thus, the movement towards specific goals of education begins with the analysis (or creation) of the social situation of personality development, since it is the starting point in the organization of the educational process (both in an educational institution and in a family). The social situation of personality development is determined, firstly, by the peculiarities of the social environment, life events, and secondly, by the peculiarity of the attitude of the educated person to the phenomena of the external environment.

That is why our "National Model" is given special attention in the system of continuous education. Another aspect of the social need in the education of young people is the formation of a healthy lifestyle. In this regard, independence gave our people the opportunity to determine their own way of life, that is, its content, and they began to live a life specific to our people. The key factor in achieving such happiness was the national-state policy of the head of our state.

"Healthy lifestyle", "Healthy generation", "Healthy faith", "Healthy people", "Healthy mind", "Healthy environment", "Harmonious generation", "Perfect person" and similar concepts and etc. dreams have become the basis of the life of our people. They have risen to the level of state policy in raising the socio-spiritual image of our country. The conclusion is made about the importance of ensuring the effectiveness of the formation of knowledge, skills and abilities in the field of spiritual education of students based on innovative technologies, continuous implementation of a training system and dissemination of promising experience and directions.

The university is a special educational space and serves not only to transfer special knowledge, but also to develop and reproduce a special cultural layer of society, the most important element of which is a specialist in the field of education. Education is an important part of the

educational activities of the university. Purposeful educational work carried out at the university covers various aspects of the life of student youth, including social assistance and support, civil, patriotic, aesthetic education based on national and universal values.

Distinguish between natural and social environments, each of which consists of different elements and has a different meaning for the development of the child's personality, affects him in different ways.

A feature of the process of introducing a developing personality to national values is the activation of higher mental functions of a person and the presence of an ethno-cultural context of individual personal growth. Therefore, there is a need for specially coordinated teachers, methodologists for the selection and implementation of optimal ways, means, forms and methods of "growing" the human personality into the sphere of national cultural values.

Thus, the social situation of personality development, when performing these pedagogical actions, turns into an educational situation of development, which can correct, change the shortcomings of the conditions and circumstances of a student's life, become an impulse for his social, moral and spiritual development

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